

DEVELOPMENT OF CET-ENCRYPTION THEORY: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

N. Lada, V. Larin, S. Rudnytskyi, H. Haponenko, D. Holovniak, Yu. Rudnytska, S. Briankin

Abstract: *The purpose of this study is a comprehensive review and analysis of scientific publications devoted to the development of the theory of cryptographic encoding (CET-encryption theory). In the process of research, published scientific results were analyzed, organized and structured. Based on the results of a comprehensive review and analysis of publications, the relationships between the formulated tasks and the obtained scientific results were established, the influence of the obtained results on the further tasks was investigated. The theoretical background, development history and practical application of CET-encryption were discussed. Through a detailed study of different types of CET-operations and methods of their transformation, the aim was to offer insight into various ways of their effective application in real-world encryption scenarios. The presented results of a comprehensive review of publications are aimed at increasing the interest of scientists in the development of CET-encryption. This interest is based on the possibility of transition from the design requirements of cryptographic systems to the requirements for the synthesis of CET-operations and groups of CET-operations. The reverse transition from the synthesized CET-operation to the cryptographic system will ensure the achievement of the requirements set for the developers. The wide variety of CET-operations, their groups and the available possibilities of automation of the research process ensure the implementation of this concept.*

Keywords: limited resources cryptography, post-quantum cryptography, cryptographic coding, stream encryption, CET-encryption, CET-operations, two-operand operations, Information systems, data-controlled permutations, a Comprehensive Review.

1. Introduction

The contribution of cryptographic protection of information to the global development of information technologies is undeniable. A reliably protected information environment has a positive effect on social progress and intellectual development. In addition, in the conditions of a hybrid war, it significantly affects the information and national security of the country. Considering modern challenges and information threats, the level of which is growing every year, leading public institutions and private organizations recognize cybersecurity as one of the main factors for them to function successfully. The governments of the world's leading countries strive to ensure an adequate level of cybersecurity at various levels through the support and development of cryptography. This issue is especially relevant due to the advent of quantum supercomputers, which will make most of the existing cryptographic information protection technologies vulnerable. Thus, there is an

urgent need to create a new theory and methodology for the synthesis of post-quantum computer cryptography systems, which should be a significant contribution to the "cyber-safe" future. One of such new theories opposing post-quantum cryptanalysis could be the theory of CET-encryption, which includes the technology of building cryptographic information protection systems based on multi-criteria synthesis of operations. In addition, another global trend in the development of information technologies is the low resource capacity of devices that require reliable protection. Today, low-resource cryptography is at the forefront of cryptographic science. Low-resource cryptography allows one to ensure high performance of the cryptosystem with a significant limitation of computing and energy resources of the object of protection.

Cryptographic encoding is considered to be one of the promising areas of development of low-resource cryptography. In the process of cryptographic encoding, cryptographic encoding operations are implemented. The selection of operations is carried out under the control of a pseudo-random sequence, which is implemented by a cryptographic algorithm.

The main goal of this work is the review and analysis of scientific works devoted to the development of the theory of cryptographic encoding (CET-encryption), which will allow to organize and structure the published scientific results. A comprehensive review and analysis of publications provides an opportunity to establish relationships between tasks and results, as well as the impact of the obtained results on formulation of further tasks. This will make it possible to determine approximate directions for further research.

2. A Comprehensive Review

Let's consider the main difference between encryption and cryptographic encoding. The use of a cryptographic algorithm for information encryption ensures the randomness of the encryption result. The encryption result depends on the key encryption algorithm and the information being encrypted. In practical applications, the encryption algorithm usually is not changed. Encryption keys and encrypted information are changed. When building cryptographic algorithms, requirements for encryption keys are formulated. Fulfillment of these requirements should ensure the necessary quality of cryptographic transformation. However, the developers of cryptographic algorithms do not consider the requirements for the information to be encrypted. Currently, any arbitrary information can be encrypted with a known cryptographic algorithm and compliance with key stability requirements. Since the information will be random, the encryption result will also be random, and this process cannot guarantee the fulfillment of the requirements for the results of the transformation of blocks of information.

The operation of cryptographic encoding implements a substitution table that guarantees the fulfillment of the requirements for the results of the transformation of a block of information. A pseudo-random sequence of cryptographic encoding operations leads to pseudo-random encryption results. Since each operation of cryptographic encoding guarantees the fulfillment of the requirements for the results of the transformation of a block of information, the encryption results will also be guaranteed to meet the established requirements set by the cryptosystem developer.

The main results of the study of cryptographic encryption operations and the results of cryptographic encoding are given in monographs [1-6]. However, the data of the publication do not reflect all the features of the development of CET-encryption, and do not focus on those tasks that were not being solved or were not solved.

The first research results of cryptographic encoding operations were published in 2006 [7]. This work presented models of logical devices that provide conversion of two bits of information. The model of cryptographic transformation operation (discrete device for cryptographic transformation of information) is built on the basis of elementary functions. According to the results of further research [8 – 10], the technology of constructing logical functions for two-digit discrete devices of cryptographic transformation of information was proposed in [11].

Further research was aimed at studying the regularities of combining elementary functions in cryptographic transformation operations. Based on the obtained results of modeling and selection of logical functions for cryptography [12, 13], methods of constructing cryptographic transformation operations based on combining elementary functions were developed [14]. In the course of further research, a number of methods for synthesis of models of discrete devices for encoding and decoding information were proposed [15, 16]. After establishing the relationships between direct and inverse operations, a model of a unified device for cryptographic transformation of information was proposed [17]. Based on the study of the order of logical functions selection and their implementation complexity, sets of command codes for unified device control were proposed, which ensure increased reliability and performance of information protection systems [18, 19]. To assess the possibility of practical implementation of two-digit cryptographic encoding operations, they were examined for compliance with the avalanche effect [20]. For this purpose, the properties of tables of minimum Hamming code distances were investigated [21] and a method of their synthesis was proposed [22].

The application of cryptographic encoding operations can be used to increase the security of confidential information resources and increase the speed of access to them. As a rule, information resources in the database are encrypted based on the database key (or keys). The subscriber must receive the necessary resources encrypted on the basis of their private key. In the process of servicing the subscriber, confidential information must be decrypted by the operator and encrypted using the subscriber's key. Works [23, 24] show the possibility of re-encrypting confidential information from a database encrypted by a database key into one encrypted by a user's key. In the re-encryption process, the database (information resource) administrator can't access the decrypted information. It should be noted that the implementation of this approach leads to the replacement of the decryption (decoding) and encryption (encoding) processes by one process – re-encryption (recoding). The results of research on the construction of models of operations of cryptographic transcoding of information are given in [25]. The obtained scientific results served as the basis for the creation of a methodology for increasing the efficiency of access to confidential information resources [26]. Works [27, 28] deal with the practical implementation of the proposed methodology. Unfortunately, the obtained scientific and practical results make it possible to fully implement this methodology only on the basis of the use of two-digit operations of cryptographic encoding.

Having summarized the results of the research of two-digit elementary functions and the two-digit cryptographic encoding operations built on their basis, the algebraic structure of the set of logical encoding operations was established [29]. In this work, it was proved that the studied set of transformations represents a group of permutations in the G_4 field, and the operation models formalize the substitution tables that implement these operations. The generalized results of the study of two-digit elementary functions and two-digit cryptographic encoding operations are given in [2]. It should be noted that obtaining the given scientific results became possible only after conducting computational experiments, which ensured the formation of the necessary base of models.

In order to increase the reliability and controllability of ciphergrams built on the basis of cryptographic encoding operations, the possibility of using redundant positional counting systems when constructing elementary functions was investigated [30, 31]. According to the results of the research, a method of cryptographic encoding of information was built with the introduction of information redundancy based on two-digit logic functions [32].

The simplicity of the study of two-digit operations of cryptographic encoding is based on the fact that these operations are described by the smallest group in terms of the number of elements, only 24 operations. The study of three-digit cryptographic transformation operations is related to the study of the group of operations in the G_8 field, which is already 40,320 operations that are built on the basis of 70 three-digit elementary functions [3].

The results of the study of a set of three-digit elementary functions and cryptographic transformation operations are given in [33, 34]. To simplify the research of the entire set of obtained elementary functions, they were divided into direct (35 elementary functions) and inverse (35 elementary functions). The division was implemented similarly to the division of two-digit elementary functions [14]. However, when studying cryptographic encoding operations built on the basis of only direct or only inverse elementary functions, it is necessary to study 5040 operations. The simultaneous analysis of such a large number of operations significantly complicates the research process. To reduce the number of cryptographic encoding operations that need to be simultaneously investigated, it is necessary to divide the groups of direct and inverse elementary functions into subgroups. In work [35] it was proposed to use the complexity of discrete models of three-digit elementary functions for the classification of these functions.

According to the classification results, both elementary functions on the basis of which permutation operations are built and elementary functions on the basis of which matrix operations of cryptographic transformation of information are built were singled out. Elementary functions for matrix operations are built on the basis of addition modulo two. Permutation operations and matrix operations provide a linear transformation of information, provided there is no additional jamming. Nonlinear information transformation is provided by operations of cryptographic transformation of information that are built on the basis of elementary functions of information-driven permutations, elementary functions of information-driven operations, and elementary functions of extended matrix cryptographic transformation [36].

It should be noted that the need to classify three-digit elementary functions and three-digit operations of cryptographic encoding is related not so much to a large

number of operations, but to the need to use a different mathematical apparatus for description. The results of the study of methods of recording specialized logical functions and three-digit cryptographic operations for their modeling and research are given in [37, 38].

Matrix cryptographic encoding operations are the only group of operations that implements linear transformation of information. The elementary functions of matrix cryptographic encoding, and as a consequence the operations of matrix cryptographic encoding, are built on the basis of addition modulo two. The method of synthesis of linear matrix operations of cryptographic transformation of information is given in [39]. However, on the basis of elementary functions of matrix cryptographic encoding, it is possible to construct operations described by binary logical matrices, and operations whose description requires an additional vector transformation. These transformations of information are described by a combination of discrete linear transformations based on addition modulo two and additional gambling modulo two. For the synthesis of these operations, an improved method of synthesis of cryptographic transformation operations was developed on the basis of the discrete-and-algebraic representation of operations [40]. Since the set of matrix cryptographic transformation operations represents a mathematical group, for each direct operation there is an inverse transformation operation that also belongs to this group. The results of the study of interrelationships between direct and inverse three-digit matrix operations are given in [41]. As a result of the generalization of the given results, a method of synthesis of matrix models of operations of cryptographic encoding and decoding of information for any number of variables (bits of input information) was built [42]. To increase the speed of access to protected information resources, the synthesis of recoding operations for a group of three-digit matrix operations was studied [43]. According to the research results, a method of synthesis of matrix models of cryptographic transcoding operations for any number of variables was built [44].

When implementing the method of information protection on the basis of matrix operations of cryptographic transformation [45], it was noted that the complexity of implementation is proportional to the square of the number of variables in the models. In order to reduce the complexity of implementing matrix cryptographic transformations, the group use of operations of a lower digit rate is proposed in works [46, 47]. The essence of this approach is the two-stage implementation of the transformation. At the first stage, a preliminary matrix transformation of groups of input signals is implemented, at the second stage, a matrix transformation of the results of the preliminary transformation is implemented. The results of the study of the mathematical model of the two-operand group matrix cryptographic transformation are given in [48]. Subsequently, the synthesis of operations of inverse group matrix cryptographic transformation of information was investigated [49], and a mathematical model of the synthesis of operations of inverse group matrix cryptographic transformation was built [50]. The results of evaluating the speed of implementation of the group matrix cryptographic transformation are given in [51].

The main results of the study of three-digit elementary functions and operations of nonlinear extended matrix cryptographic encoding are given in works [36, 52]. The description of nonlinear operations of extended matrix cryptographic encoding can be reduced to the combination of the linear part of the cryptographic transformation with subsequent addition according to the modulo of the result of the nonlinear part of the transformation [52]. Features of practical implementation of three-digit operations of extended matrix cryptographic transformation for information protection are given in [53].

To ensure the possibility of constructing operations of an arbitrary number of input variables, it was necessary to conduct a study of the conditions of non-degeneracy of the operations of the extended matrix cryptographic transformation [54, 55]. For those works it was proposed to use the method of numbering specialized logical functions [56] and the method of logical determinants [57]. The obtained scientific results made it possible to build models of inverse nonlinear operations of matrix cryptographic transformation [58, 59] and provided the possibility of synthesis of the operations themselves [60]. On the basis of the synthesis of models of inverse nonlinear operations of matrix cryptographic transformation, a generalized method of synthesis of inverse nonlinear operations of extended matrix cryptographic transformation was substantiated and built [61, 62]. Specific features of the practical implementation of operations of extended matrix cryptographic transformation of an arbitrary number of variables are given in [63, 64].

In the classification of three-digit elementary functions by the complexity of hardware implementation, the elementary functions of permutations controlled by information deserve special attention [65]. In the hardware implementation of these elementary functions, the result of the permutation depends both on the function itself and on the information received at the inputs of the discrete device. It should be noted that the complexity of the hardware implementation of the elementary function of permuting the controlled information coincides with the complexity of the operation of two-digit addition modulo two. Based on this, these elementary functions are sometimes called elementary functions of minimal complexity. The results of research and synthesis of elementary functions of permutations controlled by information are given in [66, 67]. Elementary functions and operations of permutations controlled by information are described by discrete and discrete-and-algebraic models, and they differ significantly from models of matrix and extended matrix operations [68]. Based on this, further studies were directed to the synthesis and analysis of only operations of the base group [69, 70]. When building a complete group of permutation operations controlled by information, it is necessary to perform permutation operations and additional jamming of the transformation results over the operations of the basic group. Peculiarities of implementation of information-controlled permutation operations are given in [71, 72].

Among the classified groups of elementary functions [35], the group of elementary functions of operations controlled by information remains unconsidered. This group includes 8 elementary functions on the basis of which 192 cryptographic encoding operations are built, of which 4 are basic ones [73]. Elementary functions of operations controlled by information are described by discrete-and-algebraic models, however, these models differ from models of elementary functions of permutations controlled by information and require the use of another mathematical apparatus to

formalize the synthesis of operations [73]. The insignificant number of elementary functions and operations, the complexity of their discrete-and-algebraic models and the lack of a mathematical apparatus for automating the synthesis became the reason that the elementary functions of information-driven operations and cryptographic transformation operations built on their basis were practically not studied. The necessity and expediency of conducting studies of these operations will be only after the creation of a single universal approach for describing nonlinear operations of cryptographic encoding [74]. The first attempts to use the discrete-and-casual representation of models of nonlinear elementary functions and cryptographic encoding operations are presented in [75].

The given results of the research of elementary functions and operations related to the study of the totality of operations as a whole. Classification of operations, synthesis and analysis of operations of classified groups were carried out. However, the classified and researched groups of operations represent only a part of the entire set of operations. There is a much larger number of cryptographic transformation of information operations (operations in the field of permutations), each of which is described by elementary functions from various classified groups. This approach can be considered to be fundamental and the work on its implementation should be continued, because its results are the basis for solving other scientific problems.

Another approach consists in the search and synthesis of cryptographic transformation operations that provide effective solutions to applied problems. For example: synthesis of operations that ensure maximum uncertainty of encryption results; synthesis of operations that effectively implement the coupling of blocks during sliding encryption, synthesis of operations that are advisable to be used in steganography, in the creation of watermarks, etc. Let's consider options for solving practical problems in more detail.

Publications [76, 77] deal with the analysis of cryptographic transformation operations according to the criterion of the strict avalanche effect, which can be interpreted as the criterion of the maximum uncertainty of the transformation. On the basis of the obtained results, a method of synthesis of cryptographic coding operations was developed according to the criterion of strict stable encoding [78, 79]. The method of synthesis of operations of strict stable cryptographic encoding of minimum complexity proposed in [80] is based on the use of inversion of half the bits of input information and even permutations. The criterion of strict stable cryptographic encoding will be achieved by inverting one of the pairs of bits that are swapped. According to the research results, it was found that repeating the operation of strict stable cryptographic encoding does not lead to improvement of conversion results, and in some cases it can only worsen the quality of the ciphertext with a guaranteed increase in encryption time [81 – 83].

The results of research of the possibility of improving sliding encryption algorithms based on the application of matrix cryptographic encoding operations are presented in [84, 85]. The results of modeling sliding encryption primitives based on recurrent sequences [86] provided the possibility of their parallel implementation [87]. The proposed multi-operation multiple sliding encryption [88] ensured an increase in the cryptographic strength of ciphersgrams due to the use of cryptographic encoding operations that belong to different mathematical groups.

Cryptographic encoding operations provide increased concealment of the embedded message in steganographic systems [89]. The use of cryptographic encoding operations made it possible to develop a method of embedding a steganomessage based on a key element [90]. According to the results of the study of the statistical properties of the methods of numbering blocks of stegocontainers [91], an improved method of embedding a steganomessage based on a key element was proposed [92]. For the developed methods, ways of increasing the reliability of transmission of the key element of the stegocontainer are proposed [93, 94].

Cryptographic encoding operations can be used to ensure the authenticity of electronic documents [95]. To increase the probability of detecting the facts of falsification of electronic documents, a number of hash function calculation methods based on the use of cryptographic encoding matrix operations have been proposed [96]. Detection of falsification allows establishing only the fact of a cyber attack. Detecting the distortion of an electronic document with additional detailing of the falsified fragment [97] allows one to get additional information to search for the attacker or the customer of the attack. Specific features of digital watermark formation for electronic documents based on matrix cryptographic encoding operations are considered in [98].

The considered operations of cryptographic encoding ensure the transformation of several bits, or bytes of input information into output information. As a rule, the number of bits of input information coincides with the number of bits of the ciphertext (with the exception of cases where there is information redundancy). The considered operations of cryptographic encoding were called single-operand operations [6]. At this stage of the research, the main idea of the practical application of cryptographic encoding operations was their sequential selection based on a pseudo-random sequence. To implement this idea, software or hardware implementation of the entire set of operations was necessary. However, this approach is not always justified when implementing low-resource information protection systems. With this approach, the complexity of the protection system is directly proportional to the number of cryptographic encoding operations that are used.

Further research was aimed at reducing the complexity of implementing a cryptographic system while maintaining a given number of selected single-operand operations. This goal can be achieved by moving from one-operand to two-operand operations. The first results of the study of two-operand operations of cryptographic transformation were obtained from the data of computational experiments [99, 100].

Algorithms for stream encryption are implemented on the basis of sequential addition according to modulo two pieces of information with a pseudo-random sequence. The basic operation – the operation of addition modulo two is one of the CET operations. This operation contains two operands, the first operand is the operand into which information is received and the second operand is the operand for the pseudo-random sequence. Let the two-operand operation implement the simultaneous transformation of several bits of information. As a result of the operation, the value of the second operand is added to the value of the first operand. This operation can be interpreted as adding the value of the second operand to the value of the first operand. When implementing a two-operand operation, some bits of both the first and the second operands may be inverted.

The results of the study of a set of cryptographic addition operations are given in [101]. The two-digit two-operand addition modulo two operation can be represented by a set of four two-digit single-operand matrix operations that perform the transformation of the first operand depending on the value of the second operand. The second operand will determine which of the one-operand operations will perform the conversion of the first operand. Works [102 – 105] deal with the study of interrelationships between operations in matrix models of cryptographic transformation. In the process of research, it was found that the permutation of operands and the inversion of digits modify the operation of addition according to modulo two. Modified operations can be symmetric and asymmetric [106, 107]. In works [108, 109] methods of synthesis and analysis of modified cryptographic addition modulo two operations are considered. The operation research technology based on addition modulo two is proposed [110]. According to the results of practical implementation, it was established that the modified two-digit two-operand addition modulo two operation can be used in stream ciphers if it implements at least four models of one-operand operations [111, 112]. The use of this technology made it possible to increase the reliability of the cryptographic system, which became an additional incentive for further research [6].

Symmetric two-operand operations hold a special place among the two-operand operations of cryptographic encoding, because they can be used both in the construction of stream and block ciphers. The results of the study of a group of symmetric two-digit two-operand operations on the basis of addition modulo two are given in [113 – 116]. Methods of synthesis of groups of symmetric modified two-digit two-operand operations of addition modulo two [117], modulo four [118] and right-handed addition modulo four [119] were developed. However, the main difficulty in the practical construction of groups of symmetric modified two-operand operations of cryptographic encoding is the need to know the given operation in advance. This operation is the starting point for the implementation of the developed methods. The work [120] deals with solving the problem of finding unique symmetric multi-digit two-operand cryptographic encoding operations. Works [121 – 124] deal with the practical implementation of symmetric operations in stream ciphers.

Further increase in the stability and variability of cryptographic transformations is associated with the need to study and apply asymmetric operations of cryptographic encoding. Works [125, 126] deal with the study of sets of two-operand asymmetric cryptographic encoding operations. According to the research results, asymmetric two-operand operations were divided into double and triple cycle operations [126]. Specific features of the construction of asymmetric operations lead to the need to use different methods of their synthesis [127 – 129].

The combination of symmetric and asymmetric, as well as linear and nonlinear cryptographic encoding operations in stream ciphers provides an increase in cryptographic strength [130].

The use of groups of cryptographic encoding operations in stream ciphers becomes more effective when generators of pseudo-random sequences of operations are implemented [131].

To increase the stability of stream ciphers, it was proposed to build two-operand operations from one-operand operations that meet predetermined requirements [132]. To achieve the maximum uncertainty of stream encryption results, it was proposed to use single-operand operations that meet the criterion of strict stable cryptographic encoding [133]. Since all single-operand operations meet the requirements of the criterion of strict stable cryptographic encoding, regardless of the value of the second operand, the encryption result will also meet the criterion of strict stable cryptographic encoding. This observation became the basis for the synthesis of two-operand operations of strict stable cryptographic encoding. Technologies for constructing direct [134] and inverse [135] operations of strict stable encoding are proposed in works [134, 135]. However, the increase in the digit rate of operations significantly complicates the process of their construction. The technology for constructing a two-operand four-digit operation of minimum complexity for strict stable cryptographic encoding was proposed in the work [136]. Works [137, 138] deal with the synthesis of inverse two-digit two-operand operations of cryptographic encoding. The technology for building models of four-digit two-operand operations of minimal complexity for strict stable cryptographic encoding is given in [139, 140]. It should be noted that different numbers of bits of a pseudo-random sequence can be used to implement strict stable cryptographic encoding operations. For example, when encrypting four bits of information, one can use three, four, five, etc. bits of a pseudo-random sequence [141]. After all, the number of bits of a pseudo-random sequence determines the number of substitution tables implemented in the operation, which means that it determines the variability of the encryption algorithm.

A group of two-operand operations of strict stable cryptographic encoding can be built on the basis of any two-operand operation of strict stable cryptographic encoding by successive transformation of the second operand by a one-operand operation [142]. The work [143] deals with the issue of automatic generation of models of direct and inverse two-digit two-operand operations of strict stable cryptographic encoding.

A large number of two-operand operations of cryptographic encoding complicates the process of further research. Therefore, the possibilities of automation of modeling processes and research of symmetric two-operand operations of cryptographic encoding were analyzed [144, 145]. The obtained scientific results served as a basis for the construction of information technology of modeling and research of symmetric operations of cryptographic encoding [146]. The proposed hierarchical technology allows simulating symmetric and asymmetric two-operand operations and their sequences. Relying on a combined database with a knowledge base, it allows one to significantly expand the scope of research and reduce the time it takes to conduct it [147].

It should be noted that the lack of a single approach to the description of one-operand operations models of cryptographic encoding significantly complicates the modeling of two-operand operations of cryptographic encoding. It is especially difficult to describe two-operand operations models, if they include one-operand operations, which are described using different mathematical apparatus. The solution to this problem consists of defining an existing or creating a new mathematical apparatus that will ensure the unity of the modeling processes of different elementary functions and CET-operations. In works [75, 148], it was proposed for the first time

to use discrete-and-casual models of information transformation processes in cryptographic systems. Discrete-and-casual modeling of CET-operations ensures simplicity of construction and reduction of models' complexity [148]. The compatibility of discrete-and-casual models with existing discrete logic and discrete circuit design creates significant advantages for their practical implementation.

A large number of scientific results related to cryptographic encoding caused the necessity for their philosophical reimagining and generalization. The work [130] is devoted to the general and theoretical aspects of the development of CET-encryption and their possible impact on low-resource cryptography. Ways of increasing the stability of CET-encryption on the basis of managing the quality of transformation of a block of information are investigated in the paper [149].

The generalization of the research results became the starting point in the transition to the complex use of CET-operations in stream encryption systems [1, 148, 150]. In the monograph [1], based on the results of the study of the structure and architecture of CET-operations, the principles and technologies of stream encryption are proposed. In this work, transitions from CET-operations to cryptographic systems and from cryptographic systems to cryptographic networks are implemented. Emphasis is placed on the fact that the peculiarities of the functioning of stream encryption systems are determined by the properties of the CET-operations they are built on. The quality of conversion results is determined by the features of single-operand CET-operations from which groups of multi-operand operations are built. Additional confirmation of this hypothesis are the obtained scientific results from the research of stream encryption technologies based on the use of non-commutative double-cycle CET-operations [150]. The usage of information-driven CET-operations provides cross-management of the ciphergram construction, both from the key and from the information to be encrypted [148].

The combination of different CET-operations and stream encryption technologies in low-resource cryptographic systems becomes an essential basis for the creation of post-quantum low-resource cryptography.

3. Conclusions

CET-encryption theory is a relatively new direction of cryptographic science. Its founder is Doctor of Technical Sciences, Professor Volodymyr Rudnytskyi. Volodymyr Rudnytskyi became the founder of the scientific school of cryptographic encoding in Ukraine. The theory of CET-encryption combines and extends the results of scientific research in information and cyber security, mathematical modeling and computer engineering.

For the further development of the theory of CET-encryption, the determination of the next promising research in this field and the overall disclosure of its high potential, it became expedient and necessary to review the scientific achievements made in this field. In this work, an analysis of the relevant cycle of scientific works was carried out, an arrangement of already conducted research was made and their structuring was carried out.

The main advantage of CET-encryption is the possibility of transition from the design requirements of cryptographic systems to the requirements for the synthesis of CET-operations and their groups. The reverse transition from CET-operations

synthesized on the basis of established requirements to a cryptographic system will provide a solution to the tasks set before the developers. The presence of the possibility of direct and reverse transitions ensures further development of both methods of synthesis of CET-operations and cryptographic systems based on CET-encryption.

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Nataliia LADA - Candidate of Technical Sciences (PhD in Technology and Engineering), Leading Researcher, *Corresponding author*
State Scientific Research Institute of Armament and Military Equipment Testing and Certification, Cherkasy, Ukraine

Volodymyr LARIN - Associate Professor, Candidate of Technical Sciences (PhD in Technology and Engineering), Head of Department
State Scientific Research Institute of Armament and Military Equipment Testing and Certification, Cherkasy, Ukraine

Serhii RUDNYTSKYI - Associate Professor, Candidate of Technical Sciences (PhD in Technology and Engineering), Associate Professor
Cherkasy State Technological University, Cherkasy, Ukraine

Hennadii HAPONENKO - Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences (PhD in Pedagogy),
Leading Researcher
State Scientific Research Institute of Armament and Military Equipment Testing and Certification, Cherkasy, Ukraine

Dmytro HOLOVNIAK - PhD in Technology and Engineering, Head of Department
State Scientific Research Institute of Armament and Military Equipment Testing and Certification, Cherkasy, Ukraine

Yuliia RUDNYTSKA - PhD in Technology and Engineering, Senior Lecturer
Cherkasy State Technological University, Cherkasy, Ukraine

Serhii BRIANKIN - Candidate of Technical Sciences (PhD in Technology and Engineering), Leading Researcher
State Scientific Research Institute of Armament and Military Equipment Testing and Certification, Cherkasy, Ukraine